

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

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Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)	Lessons learnt and best practices on territorial change by performing roadmaps as tool for strategic territorial development and underlining the experience in implementation of action for transition of regions from classical industry to digitalised industry including RRI approach.
Key words	RRI integrated roadmap process, stakeholder engagement, transition process, digitalisation, lessons learnt

DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

Digitalised industry territories	Territories with a high level of digitalisation in their industrial sectors, i.e. a high level of digital development and usage of ICT innovations, taking into account technical, business as well as social elements (see e.g., Grundke et al., 2018).
White Book	A book or rather a paper, a written document, describing the findings of the project. A white paper is a short report or guide that succinctly summarises the essence of a complex issue to give readers quick access to an official “government” report bound in white.
SWOT	SWOT analysis is about strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats (risks) of a topic, organisation, system or any case and its environment. SWOT stands for Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats Analysis. This analysis provides the current status of the “enterprise” and can be recorded in order to derive suitable strategic optimization measures (https://www.bwl-lexikon.de/wiki/swot-analyse/).
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 DigiTeRRI the Project

The project DigiTeRRI worked out a framework and co-created roadmaps with stakeholders for a responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial innovation ecosystems by applying the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach in three European pilot regions. The roadmap was performed together with the impacted industries, the impacted science, research and education organisations, the influential territorial authorities, and the affected citizens. The creation of strategies was conducted for implementing actions contributing to a resilient innovation ecosystem for digitalised industries in traditional industry territories. The project pursued a high degree of openness, democratic accountability, and responsiveness to the needs of the addressed industries and all societal stakeholder groups in the considered regions.

DigiTeRRI project is a Coordination Support Action (CSA) with GA 873010 under H2020, SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020, supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation.

The DigiTeRRI roadmapping led to three territorial roadmaps, one for Grand-Est in France, one for Styria in Austria and one for Värmland in Sweden, to provide strategic orientation for the transition into a digitalised innovation ecosystem. The three territories brought in their different cultures as well as their individual history and shared experience in traditional industries, e.g., industrial production, steel, pulp and paper, automotive, or aerospace. Since the three DigiTeRRI territories have similar traditions in industrial production, cross-regional learning could take place in joint workshops with participants of the other territories.

DigiTeRRI targeted the following objectives:

Objective 1: Characterising and mapping the current three territorial innovation ecosystems, which provided a qualitative and quantitative stocktaking and mapping of the characteristics the engaged territories in DigiTeRRI. Their innovation ecosystems, their digitalisation degrees, and their statuses regarding RRI were evaluated and characterised at the beginning. Results provided a solid empirical analysis and visualised pictures of these three territories for a better understanding of the innovation ecosystems within their societal, economic, geographical and environmental context.

Objective 2: Generating a vision statement for each territory provided a common orientation for the development of the roadmap. It was important that this territorial vision statement was co-created by all stakeholders affected, because it created awareness and a common vision of the future of the territory.

Objective 3: Developing a roadmap (goals, objectives, identified gaps, necessary actions) was the main focus in each of the three territories together with all stakeholders, especially the agreeing on goals and objectives, and developing actions for transitioning into responsible digitalised territories. The outcome of objective 1 and objective 2 were the foundation for this objective 3 with the results of the mapping on the one hand and the vision statement on the other.

Objective 4: Implementing actions forms an indicator for the functioning of the project work and makes the first successes visible. The actions were implemented according to the developed goals and derived needs of the territories. Furthermore, the changes were monitored, conclusions drawn, and recommendations deduced.

The White Book summarizes the lessons learnt and best practices from the territories and project team for interested readers: public development institutions, local representatives, company managers, regional association, and academics.

The report is structured into the following chapters. (1) Chapter “Introduction” gives an overview about the cornerstones of DigiTeRRI project. (2) Chapter “Lessons Learnt” talks about (i) the procedure of collecting the lessons learnt and (ii) the learning learnings about the roadmapping process, the stakeholder engagement, the RRI approach in DigiTeRRI, the intra-territorial collaboration amongst the regional project team, the cross-territorial collaboration in DigiTeRRI, the implementation of the actions, and the digital transition achieved in DigiTeRRI. (3) Chapter “Conclusion” summarizes the key learnings.

The activities in DigiTeRRI have reached more than 1000 people in Europe; especially, in the three engaged industry regions, namely in Grand-Est in France, in Styria in Austria, and in Värmland in Sweden, (see Myhrén, P., 2022, D5.1, where the participants in the implementation of the actions are documented). There have been at least five workshops in each territory with various stakeholders, 20 to 60 participants in these workshops. The final conference counted 184 participants. In addition, DigiTeRRI reaches many people via social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube channel, newsletters, and the webpage).

1.2 The Three DigiTeRRI Territories

The three DigiTeRRI territories, Grand-Est, Styria, and Värmland, currently undergo the change from the traditional industrial production e.g., materials such as steel, paper and pulp production, automotive, aerospace industry, or production industry in general to a digitalised industry. Beside that same characteristic these territories are different in size and regional population size. They have different processes in generation S3 strategy and are represented by different type of organisation of their territory. These three territories built the pilot regions for the DigiTeRRI integrated approach and implementation of the transition process.

All three territories show a similar picture regarding their industry and economy structure and challenges. Many actors in these three territories act and produce locally, however, their supply chains and markets span the globe. Thus, the similarity of these three territories can be summarized in (a) the presence of traditional industries, (b) close collaboration between the industry, universities, and the government, (c) facing challenges related to digitalisation in the regional business processes and aiming to survive in a globally competitive business environment (see Nguyen et al. 2022, D4.4; Stegmann McCallion et al. 2021, D2.1; Paier et al., 2020, D2.3; Nguyen et al., 2021 D3.2; Hörlesberger et al., 2021, D4.2).

The similarities and the differences of the three territories are reflected in the application of the DigiTeRRI approach, the DigiTeRRI roadmapping process so that e.g., the stakeholders in Grand-Est are spread over a bigger area and thus can participate easier in online workshops (although, we have learnt that face-to-face workshops are more creative). The following table gives an overview about the three territories.

Table 1. Key regional indicators for the DigiTeRRI regions.

NO	REGIONAL CHARACTERISTICS	GRAND-EST (FRANCE)	STYRIA (AUSTRIA)	VÄRMLAND (SWEDEN)
1	Area	57,433 km ²	16,401 km ²	17,591 km ²
2	Population	5.53 million in 2019 (around 8.3% of the population of France in 2018)	1.24 million (2020)	281,482 (2019)
3	Regional population density	96 inhabitants per sq. km in 2019	76 inhabitants per sq. km in 2020	18 inhabitants per sq. km in 2016
4	No of counties in the country	13 territories in France	9 federal states in Austria	21 counties in Sweden
5	Largest city	Strasbourg	Graz	Karlstad
6	Population density of the largest city	3,600 inhabitants per sq. km in 2017	2,300 inhabitants per sq. km in 2020	2,035 inhabitants per sq. km
7	Number of municipalities	5,121	287	16
8	NUTS classification	FRF	AT2	SE311
9	Contribution of the region to the national GDP	7% in 2020 (153 billion euros)	12.9% in 2019 (49.6 billion euros in 2018)	1.3% in 2019
10	Region representing in organisation in the DigiTeRRI project	Region agency responsible for development of region, university, Cluster representing industry and SME	University, representative of a local city, Centre for entrepreneurship representing start-up and entrepreneurs	University, cluster for representing the typical industrial orientation in wood and paper industry, and responsible organisation for regional development

(Source Nguyen et al. 2022, D4.4, updated by AIT).

The three territories are also characterised by their developed main goals during the roadmapping process in co-creation with the stakeholders. The main goals in Värmland are, (i) utilize research and develop a common language, (ii) strengthen and maximise policy, strategy, and cultural change at organisational and territorial levels, (iii) think and act in a quadruple helix (e.g.; science, policy, industry, and society) perspective and ensuring that equity, respect for diversity, and interdependence is acknowledged, (iv) join networks to maximise collaboration and joint actions, and (v) embed cultural change in the territory organisations to highlight the impact and possibilities digitalisation delivers for all. Grand-Est main goals are (i) enable all talents in Grand Est to seize opportunities provided by the digital sector, (ii) create the conditions for the development of 'responsible' digital services and products, (iii) develop new forms of collaboration, (iv) increase social responsibility as part of a digital transformation process, (v) give as many people as possible the opportunity to discover digital technologies. Styria's main goals are (i) balanced working and living environment enhanced by digital means, (ii) co-operation of cities, research, economy and the territorial government in Styria addressing all generations, (iii) digital transformation in the field of education, science and innovation. Knowledge and technology transfer from data science to strengthen the industry of the territory, (iv) creating open work-environments and countering the lack of knowledge workers, empowering the labor force, (v) a universal platform for networking and offering up-to-date information about the region (digital marketing) (Kriszt et al., 2022).

2 LESSONS LEARNT

2.1 Procedure of collecting the lessons learnt

The lessons learnt for this white book were manifold and are collected from experiences gained in the project.

- A. *Project work*: Analysis of the learnings in the different work packages and tasks and documented in the deliverables.
- B. *DigiTeRRI team reflection*: A bottom-up analyse of all DigiTeRRI team members had reflected. In each of the three territories and all project partners co-created this analysis. These lessons learnt had been collected and classified by a SWOT¹.

The DigiTeRRI work and approach was structured into the following aspects for the SWOT analysis.

1. Roadmapping process
2. Stakeholder engagement
3. The RRI approach in DigiTeRRI
4. Intra-territorial collaboration amongst the regional project team
5. Cross-territorial collaboration in DigiTeRRI
6. Implementation of the actions
7. Digital transition achieved in DigiTeRRI

- C. *Recommendations* are deduced from both, the “project work” and the “DigiTeRRI team reflection”.

This also gave the structure for the documentation.

All lessons learnt in this White book are based (a) on the work in these 3 territories and (b) on the work in the tasks of developing the framework, the work on the comparison and monitoring, and the DigiTeRRI team reflection.

¹ a study undertaken to identify its strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats (<https://www.managementstudyguide.com/swot-analysis.htm>, <https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/display/ExactExternalWiki/SWOT+analysis+-+strengths%2C+weaknesses%2C+opportunities+and+threats>).

The SWOT methodology is originally developed for living organisations or ongoing projects. In this case of the DigiTeRRI project the activities being analysed are already over. However, this analysis here refers to the lessons learnt and recommendations. Therefore, also considering opportunities and risks bring in some meaningful points for further application of the DigiTeRRI approach. Therefore, a SWOT analysis was conducted.

2.2 Learnings from the Roadmapping Process

2.2.1 Project work on Roadmapping

Roadmapping builds a bridge between strategic and operational innovation management and has to be seen as a multistep process. It focuses on anticipation of the near future (about five years). Roadmapping describes the process of roadmap development, which is the strategic future plan. The roadmapping approach and the framework of the DigiTeRRI project is described in detail in Nguyen et al., 2021, D 3.2.

The literature describes different types of roadmapping processes (Camarinha-Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2004). For example, technology roadmaps or product roadmaps link potential markets with technologies and products and predict the chances of success of the products described. Most roadmaps concentrate on companies and their business development.

There is little literature on territorial roadmapping methodology, the transition of society or even innovation systems to a new powerful technological shift like digitalization. For example, there are technology-specific roadmaps with a regional focus such as energy roadmaps at European level, mobility roadmaps or an Austrian roadmap for high-performance metals. Very often concrete applications could be found at national or international level (e.g., on the subject of sustainability), although the methodology for creating roadmaps for a specific technology in relation to a region or a country has not yet been described in a systematic and detailed manner.

However, there were core elements and project steps that are inherent in a roadmapping process.² This common procedure was adapted to the needs of the territorial and digitalisation demand of DigiTeRRI. The DigiTeRRI roadmap process was structured into four phases (see [Figure 1](#)). The roadmap process started with stocktaking and mapping, followed by the developing of a vision statement, then generating the goals and objectives for the roadmap itself, and finally defining the necessary actions. The last phase in the roadmapping dealt with implementation of actions and evaluation. The individual steps and sub-actions such as defining the frame of analysis, identifying the stakeholders to be engaged, elaborating the framework, comparing the roadmaps, monitoring and evaluating the achievements are embedded into these four phases are shown in [Figure 1](#).

² The "Energy Technology Roadmaps. A guide to development and implementation" from International Energy Agency, 2014 presents a good foundation for a roadmapping process in a broader (technology and regional) context]

Roadmapping for the transition into a digitalised region / innovation ecosystem covers various action fields necessary for the transition. DigiTeRRI analysed the innovation ecosystem of the three European territories and came up with the following seven domains as a proposal for the action fields: (1) Knowledge & skills; (2) Technology; (3) Networks & collaboration, (4) Infrastructure; (5) Culture & values; (6) Leadership, business & market; (7) Communication. These domains were adapted by the DigiTeRRI team from Bumann and Peter (2019), who considered the digitalisation of companies. These domains were interlinked with the actors of an innovation ecosystem coming from science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public authorities, and civil society, and RRI keys as well. Note that roadmapping in the domain of digital technologies was specific as each stakeholder of the ecosystem was always both a decision maker about digitalisation and a person impacted by digitalisation.

The roadmapping process was done in several steps following the path from Phase A to Phase D in [Figure 1](#). Each of the three DigiTeRRI territories, Grand-Est in France, Styria in Austria, and Värmland in Sweden brought together the innovation ecosystem actors and co-created a vision statement (Phase B), roadmap goals, objectives, actions (Phase C), and implemented already twelve actions in the project duration (Phase D). The three individual roadmaps - the strategic plans – were outputs of Phase C. The formulation of the actions which had to be implemented was also output of Phase C as a result of the roadmapping process. Phase D was devoted to the implementation of actions which were the initiation to digital transition and to the evaluation of the roadmap impact.

The evaluation and improvement were important parts (in Phase D) of the roadmap process. A questionnaire was developed and sent to all stakeholders to learn about the understanding of the impact of the DigiTeRRI roadmapping. The feedback of the engaged stakeholders gave information on the initiation of a change process and impact of the roadmapping done by the DigiTeRRI project.

Important to note is that the DigiTeRRI roadmap process was designed and performed by engaging stakeholders of the territories (Chapter 2.3) and by an integrated RRI approach (Chapter 2.4).

The three developed roadmaps (one for Grand-Est in France, one for Styria in Austria, and one for Värmland in Sweden) built the basis for the comparison of the roadmapping processes. It shows the similarities and differences in the output of the roadmap process. The results of the comparison reflect the typology of the regions and summarizes the common aspects, the differences of the territories and their roadmap goals, objectives, and actions (Nguyen et al., 2022, D4.4). An important learning with respect to the roadmapping is that for each region a different focus and different strategy to developing key measures, and that the differences came from regional characteristics and the challenges that they need to address.

Figure 1: The four phases of the DigiTeRRI roadmapping process.

The experience that the defined roadmap process supported to deal with the differences of the territories and achieved individual results. This can be highlighted as a power and universal application option of the DigiTeRRI integrated RRI roadmap process. The DigiTeRRI roadmapping methodology turned out to be flexible enough to be used across regions with different characteristics, visions, and goals in the transition process. Each region developed their own pathways and implementation profile according to their resources, strength and needs.

DigiTeRRI integrated RRI approach is a stakeholder oriented roadmapping. The workshop work with the stakeholders is most important because these stakeholder workshops built the basis for the roadmap of each territory.

The following table presents a general logic of the development of goals, objectives, detection of gaps, definition of milestones, development of actions, set the prioritisations and timelines, which was used in the DigiTeRRI roadmapping.

Table 2. A logic of the roadmapping.

Logic Item	Description
<i>Goals:</i>	The goals are a clear and concise set of targets that, if achieved, will result in the desired outcome. A goal defines the general intentions and ambitions; however, it can be difficult to measure. The DigiTeRRI roadmap showed that the defined domain helped to address the most important goals for the territorial transition and future development.
<i>Objectives:</i>	Once a core goal is set, defining objectives is the next step towards fostering a clear understanding of how to reach the desired outcome. The main difference between objectives and goals is that objectives cover precise actions including measurable steps individuals and groups take to move closer to the goal. They are specific targets that typically have a time-bound schedule or timeline for completion. Interestingly the clustering of the goals to the objective helped to see the strategies of the territories better and to do analysis of the three territories.
<i>Milestones:</i>	Milestones are interim performance targets for achieving the goals with specific dates (e.g., “50% of the municipalities will have built the hardware for high-speed internet by Oct. 2021”). One important learning for multi organisational and stakeholder processes was, that the stakeholders often avoid giving milestones on a clear time scale, they have a focusses and clear idea about the goals but hardly bring them in a timeline in the workshops. This can be interpreted by the missing of detailed and comprehensive knowledge of the stakeholders in any events. Gathering that information needs additional resources and time and cannot be recalled at the workshops.
<i>Gaps and barriers:</i>	The roadmapping process detects a list of potential gaps in knowledge, technology limitations, market, structural barriers, regulatory limitations, public acceptance, or other barriers to achieving the goals and milestones. Depending in the culture of discussion and interaction of the stakeholder the roadmap process helped to unveil gaps. In other cases, the project teams had to analyse and deduct the gaps from the workshop input of stakeholders.
<i>Action items:</i>	The actions are developed to overcome any gaps or barriers. Actions are measures to overcome obstacles, to pave the way for achieving the goals. Typical solution actions include technology development, development of regulations and standards, policy agendas, creation of financing mechanisms, and public engagement. In the DigiTeRRI process the project team had to analyse the mentioned and derived action items, cluster them to reach a higher potential of implementation.
<i>Priorities and timelines:</i>	The actions are prioritised with timelines. The most important actions that need to be taken in order to achieve the goals and the periods will be specified. There will be interconnections among those actions. These interconnections have to be carefully considered with regard to the affected stakeholder roles and relationships. As already said by in the topic of milestones, the development of timelines or priorities has to be done in cooperation with additional workshops with selected stakeholders or even by the project team, by reflection the territorial objectives and gaps.

The DigiTeRRI roadmap process reveals that this approach is robust and very clear to be used for other regions and topics because this approach is very well structured. The development of the roadmap domains showed to be a robust structure for dealing with the transition process of territories and to derive the most important goals and objectives (based on the vision statement, see Hörlesberger et al., 2021, D3.3).

Measuring the impact of the project with innovation indicators at the system level (of the region, in this case) did not allow to identify immediate project impacts, for several reasons: Changes, e.g., in scientific output (publications), technological output (patents), or gender balance on the digital labour market will not be measurable in the region in such a short time, because education, training and research, and also changes in culture take time. Moreover, it was hardly possible to assign such a potential change to the effect of a single project like DigiTeRRI, even if such statistical data were available at short notice (which usually exhibit a substantial time-lag). These were reasons why our evaluation of the project impact was performed as a self-assessment exercise through a survey of project participants. Comparing the pre-project and the post-project assessments of different participant groups (action participants, action managers, regional stakeholders) allowed at least to evaluate the relevance, coherence and effectivity of the project in the participants' perspective.

2.2.2 Lessons learnt from the reflection of the project team

Innovation ecosystems are complex systems which are composed by the actors (stakeholders) coming from science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public authorities, and civil society. The exchange of knowledge and products, the collaboration between all these stakeholders form this innovation ecosystem. Developing futures, and in the case of DigiTeRRI a roadmap, requires a methodology which (i) covers this complexity, (ii) is simple and understandable for the co-creators (the stakeholder in the workshops), (iii) is well structured, clear, for the people in charge of the process, the DigiTeRRI team. All team members of the territories experienced the challenge of communication, tackling the multidimensional task of bringing all those aspects together. The DigiTeRRI project and thus the roadmapping was done under COVID-19 conditions which did not allow very often face-to-face meeting as stakeholder process would need. Sometimes that was experienced as a burden for the project work. However, the DigiTeRRI team learnt to work with digital tools, to perform online stakeholder meetings, to conduct virtual stakeholder workshops, to exchange and to discuss, and to co-create together using digital environments for the roadmapping process. The advantage for such a procedure could be experienced especially in large geographic regions (e.g., Grand-Est), where many stakeholders could take part in the same online workshop. For a face-to-face workshop, these stakeholders would not travel so far.

The preparation of the workshops was very important, especially under the COVID-19 situation. Planning the objectives of each workshop was crucial for the success of the roadmapping. The following items were important: (a) scheduling the workshop, (b) making available the input of the workshops, (c) formulating well understandable questions so that the stakeholders get clearly to know, how they could contribute to the objectives, (d) clarity about

to use of the workshop results, (e) which information are handed over to participants (document, timeline), (f) clearly defined benefits for the stakeholder (in the best case).

In the following the collection of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and the threats collected in the workshop team are summarizes.

Table 3. Strengths and Weaknesses of the DigiTeRRI roadmap process.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DigiTeRRI roadmap process is clear and structured. This process supports well the documentation of the results of the workshops. • This methodology provides diverse views of societal representatives and multi-layered stakeholder groups. • This process provides a complete view of regional actors including the ecosystem mapping, which gives an excellent foundation for starting a roadmapping with vision statement and goals. • This roadmap process meets especially industry, business, SMEs representatives because of the clear and well-defined structure and thus meets their expectations. • This methodology is easy to apply because no sophisticated tools are needed. There is only the need of well-prepared templates and questions. • The results are easy to communicate to engaged and committed stakeholders. • The process managed even to reach the implementation of 12 actions during the project period assisted by research experts. • COVID-19 stimulated the use of internet tools and video meetings and increased the level of experience with such tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main project work had to be done during COVID-19. Therefore, virtual / online workshops had to be organised. Virtual workshops are not optimal solutions, because online meetings are tiring and are not able to stimulate creativity. However, online meetings even better than hybrid workshops because hybrid meetings require a high effort in preparing. The creativity is much higher in physical meetings. The output is better in physical meetings. • Since there are the different types of stakeholders (namely representatives from science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public authorities, and civil society organisations) and thus, not everyone's expectations can be met. • Virtual web-meeting was a learning process. • Defining and implementing more trans-territorial actions would need more time and resources, which was not possible inside the DigiTeRRI frame.

Table 4. Opportunities and Threats of the DigiTeRRI roadmap process.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The clarity of the roadmap process keeps the engagement of the stakeholders over time, which also follows the logic of SMEs. • The DigiTeRRI process provides methodologies for other regions and topics. • The process provides a holistic view of the need of the society in a territory. • This process (including various stakeholder types) recognizes more critical topics and needs for transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The process has to be applied very carefully otherwise it would be too complex for all. • When not well prepared, planned, structured, organised the process is too complex. • Poor planning has a big impact. • The results from the mapping part could be rather complex and is not so easy to communicate to stakeholders. It needs simple and clear presentations.

The outcome of the workshop had to be documented. This requires a good structure. The workshop results had to be summarized and often interpreted after each workshop. The subsequent step is built on the previous one. Therefore, it is very important to produce high quality output in each step. In the best case, all stakeholders involved in the project work should be informed and aware of the whole process, which goes over several months.

2.2.3 Recommendations regarding the roadmap process

The roadmapping process needs a very clear planning. A timeline within 6 months (not longer than) with a very clear structure and set of questions would meet conditions for a stakeholder involvement. This planning needs particular attention and management resources. The stakeholder should be motivated to think about the roadmap workshop question in advance to get more reflected idea and reach a better timeline of the milestones and actions to be improved.

The stocktaking and mapping are an important starting point. However, communicating the results from the mapping could be rather complex. It needs simple, visual, and clear presentation so that it is understandable for one day workshop participants in a short time. The challenge is very often to get the right indicators and data base. This needs sometimes to consider asking the stakeholders in advance but give them a framework for evaluation their system (see questionnaire on self-assessment according to digital mature status of territories in Boly et al. 2021, D2.4). An evaluation of the roadmap impact (at the end of the project) by questionnaire of the engaged stakeholders should be preferred instead of an analysis based on published statics data, because of the short time span.

Communicating the vocabulary about roadmapping (this includes differences between goals / actions, the concept of future, temporal dimensions short versus long term) and digital transition (digitization, digitalisation, inclusion among other) requires time, once in the preparation and once in the workshop. The participating stakeholders should understand in a short time what they have to contribute. The analysis and the interpretation of the workshop outcome should be done by a multidiscipline team representing actors from science, industry and public administration, because the logic of the different disciplines should reflect the workshop results. The team should also be gender balanced to bring in the different views of male and females.

The process for creating the visual presentation, the graphics and visuals of the vision statements and roadmaps was an iterative mutually enriching exercise. The created visuals and graphics supported the communication of the content optimally. The vision statement is better understandable and transparent for all the territorial stakeholder by visualisation. Visual presentations of the results are quite a strong tool for bringing complex terms down to earth. Including illustrations, pictures and visualizations as part of the process may help unblocking biases and increase acceptance.

Having a local team member coordinating the inputs from the various participating stakeholders was a key success factor. The process may go slower, but the legitimacy and acceptance of the outcome are very high.

Extra attention has to be put on clear, inclusive, ethic, and respectful visual concepts in line with the RRI principles.

The project team, which must apply this DigiTeRRI roadmapping process, needs some experience in applying this methodology to achieve good result. This needs a training of the overall project member, being involved in the roadmapping process, being a moderator in the workshop or have any other function in the roadmapping process. As already mentioned, in large territories, online workshops engage more stakeholders, because they do not need to travel. However, online workshops do not stimulate so much the creativity and are more tiring. Some workshops can be prepared by informative online meetings with stakeholders, so that the face-to-face workshop can run more smoothly. Therefore, DigiTeRRI and COVID-19 have taught us to design and plan a good mixture of both, online and face-to-face workshops.

Monitoring the whole innovation ecosystem at the end of the project to detect the changes in this innovation ecosystem, in the case of DigiTeRRI in the topic “digitalisation” is not possible, because the changes could not be made visible in the corresponding databases in such a short time span of 3 years (project duration). The scientific literature, the patents, the developed projects indicating these changes, are not available in this short time. Therefore, an online questionnaire was developed, and the engaged stakeholders and the affected people have been questioned and the answers have been analysed. It turned out that this procedure is a very good tool for getting a meaningful overview of the impact of the project work.

2.3 Stakeholder engagement

2.3.1 Project work in stakeholder engagement

A very important part in DigiTeRRI was the engagement of stakeholders. For the DigiTeRRI integrated RRI approach stakeholder engagement is crucial. The stakeholder affected by the core topic, namely digitalisation of innovation ecosystem of a territory, co-create together the future. The stakeholders learned about the current situation through the mapping and stocktaking. Next, they developed the vision statement. They co-created the goals, the objectives, etc.

Within the DigiTeRRI project a systematic procedure for the stakeholder engagement was developed. This comprised of three main phases ([Table 5](#)).

Table 5. Phases of stakeholder interaction in the DigiTeRRI project.

PHASES	ACTION
Identification	Selection of the stakeholder organizations or individuals according to a specific definition of groups and/or competences
Involvement	Introduce the DigiTeRRI project to stakeholders, inform about the project objectives, explain the benefits of the project for them; invited them to participate in the project
Engagement	Active contribution of the stakeholder in the project

Before stakeholders were engaged two more phases had to be passed. By definition of the project proposal these were stakeholder identification, stakeholder involvement and stakeholder engagement. The stakeholder identification dealt with selection of the stakeholder organisations or individuals according to a specific criterion of groups and/or competences, but also, from the stocktaking/mapping in which key stakeholders were detected. The stakeholder involvement introduced stakeholders to the DigiTeRRI project, informed about the project objectives, explained the benefits of the project for them, invited them to participate in the project. The stakeholder engagement in DigiTeRRI offered active contribution to the project work. The roles and the needs for stakeholders were manifold. Stakeholders represent the territories. They reflect the values, build the knowledge base and are the innovation drivers. They are the key actors in the process of roadmapping of DigiTeRRI because:

- The stakeholder organisations represent the territories in different roles and levels. Thus, they represent different relevant social groups of territorial society being addressed or even affected by digitalisation.

- They are responsible partners of the territories with respect to the innovative orientation of the territories.
- They have the power to anticipate the impact of new trends and developments.
- Stakeholders have to be willing to support the roadmap with their own resources, when contributing to the roadmap process, most of them would need resources (e.g., time or travel costs). It is favourable that some stakeholder organisations have knowledge on digitalisation. The regional transition in DigiTeRRI was more successful if the engaged stakeholders had the power, legitimation, and urgency for a change (Mitchell et al., 1977).
- Stakeholder target groups have different profiles in establishing and implementing the DigiTeRRI roadmap and thus these different profiles are needed to cover and meet a broader section of the innovation ecosystem.

The engagement of the stakeholders was a crucial issue and should be dedicated to a specific task and should get enough resources. In the preparation phase, the stakeholders had to be informed in detail about the objectives and procedure in the project, starting with the mapping and its results, the development of the vision statement, and how to co-create the goals and objectives of the roadmap (see also Kriszt, 2020, D3.1).

This phase needed some introductory talks, pre-meetings or seminars on digitalisation, on roadmapping, on RRI in advance. Stakeholders had the opportunity to undergo a learning process about the project goals and territorial needs. A good knowledge of the stakeholders about the DigiTeRRI project and its goals was essential for a fruitful co-creation process in the roadmap development. The RRI approach was presented at the beginning of the roadmap process to the contributors as the vocabulary, history and associated European values with the intention to help embracing new digital perspectives. The challenge was huge to reach as many stakeholders as possible and to provide the right information and knowledge to them. The stakeholders understood that this new approach was not a reconsideration of their own past activities but a way to find synergies between initiatives and to seek for a more responsible general development and bring more added values to innovations.

For reaching these stakeholders, a communication concept for engaging stakeholders was needed. This communication concept was not only linked to the attendance of stakeholders in the workshops and to get a sufficient number of participants representing the Quadruple Helix, but also to making the objectives, process, and outcomes available to a wider audience. This maximised the impact at the territorial level and to ensure and to continue the discussions after the project will be over. Communication for promoting the project context and actions to a broad and multitude audiences played a crucial role. DigiTeRRI had used social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube channel, newsletters, and the webpage). The analysis of this activities uncovered a broad reach of people (see Kriszt, 2021, D4.1).

All three territories Styria, Grand-Est and Värmland had a remarkable potential of stakeholder engagement in the planned roadmapping process. The identified stakeholder matrices fulfilled all the requirements according to the Quadruple Helix Innovation model for regions and the RRI process dimensions/keys approach. Each territory had a representative number of the different types of stakeholder organisations. They either were especially affected by the digital transition or had an active role as experts (see Kriszt, 2021).

The stakeholder engagement process was performed in a similar way in all three territories. All processes were democratic, participative and gender equal. This guarantees that Styria, Grand-Est and Värmland developed a stakeholder matrix, which is typical for each territory. Even if some similarities, especially in business orientation according to the S3 classification was found, each stakeholder matrix was unique and gave the individual picture of the territory which was typically for the visioning process in a roadmap process (see Kriszt, 2021).

2.3.2 Lessons learnt from stakeholder-oriented co-creation processes

DigiTeRRI applied a very clear and focused procedure for engaging stakeholders. The management of stakeholder engagement was crucial. The individual stakeholder groups in general think differently and have a different acting structures. Knowledge of this was very helpful in order to be able to adequately address the different stakeholder groups. The size of a region played an important role. Bringing together stakeholders from the five DigiTeRRI stakeholder groups from a large region was difficult. Online workshop made it possible to reach stakeholders in a geographically big area. Building subgroups in subregions supported the engagement of a wider stakeholder group.

Table 6. Strength and Weaknesses of the stakeholder engagement in DigiTeRRI.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The stakeholder engagement created a wider perspective on the challenges and requirements for the transition. • It covers the perspectives of society in a broader way and brought in contributions from a wide range of groups. • Bringing together the different actors of an innovation ecosystem was excellent for generating ideas. • The collaboration of different stakeholder groups (here in DigiTeRRI the Quadruple Helix actors) rose mutual interest. • It created new networks and collaboration inside the stakeholder organisations. • Stakeholder engagement in developing the roadmap also supported the implementation of the measures and actions defined during the roadmapping process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In DigiTeRRI there were several stakeholder workshops, starting with the vision statement development in one workshop, defining the goals and objectives in a next workshop, etc. It is very difficult to always get the same stakeholders for each workshop. There can be a loss of continuity of stakeholder engagement and process of roadmapping. • Attracting SMEs for the whole project was hard and hardly possible because the SMEs would need resources (time and costs). • Stakeholders focused on their own benefit. • Getting stakeholders to attend multiple workshops over a period of time took effort, which was underestimated. The organisers had to motivate them, developed a concept on the benefits for stakeholders and presented this concept appropriately. Incentives would support the stakeholder participation. • Following up on the results of the previous workshop was not easy with the stakeholders. The stakeholders brought in new points of views in each of the workshops, although they had participated in the previous workshop. This required a very clear and structured introduction to the workshops bringing in the results of the last workshop for getting a common understanding. • An online participation reduced levels of personal interactions during the process.

Table 7. Opportunities and Threats of the stakeholder engagement in DigiTeRRI.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When a business cluster or business network has already good relationship to its members, attracting the stakeholders was not so difficult, otherwise it had been a challenge to get adequate stakeholders interested in the project. • To know the actors of the territory and their missions is very helpful for creating benefits for themselves and for creating results for the project. • It is a good opportunity to exchange experience between actors on regional and European level (the partners in DigiTeRRI and the stakeholder groups in the other DigiTeRRI regions during workshops or action events). • The DigiTeRRI roadmapping process made it to get stakeholders ready to participate in implementing actions. • A great opportunity is the co-creation of ideas based on the various perspectives of the stakeholders. • Establishing a core group of stakeholders proved very helpful in the ongoing work and in disseminating the results. • An ongoing dialogue within this core stakeholder group was of great value to finetune the content in the workshops. It was also vital to keep up the interest for the forthcoming actions in the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While missing a change agent or a stronger commitment of the regional opinion leaders the roadmap results cannot reach the highest impact. • One condition of the DigiTeRRI approach for selecting stakeholders was that the stakeholder group should have representatives from the five groups such as science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public authorities, and civil society organisations. The different level of knowledge regarding digitalisation is therefore a challenge and a risk for the project work. • Stakeholder groups are perfect for idea generation and new impulses in a roadmap process. For implementation more powerful and dedicated partners are needed in the most cases, which refers to power, legitimacy, ability to implement, and financial - and human resources. • Due to the overrepresentation of large enterprises, it was their needs that were addressed. We might have missed out some of the needs of SMEs. • The risk level was low. The stakeholders mainly engaged to follow up the actions. • Hardly any organisation could be found that represents the interest of regional civil society.

2.3.3 Recommendations for stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement took specific attention. It needed resources and separated tasks. The project plan may include such stakeholder management tasks. These tasks required persuasion, establishing contacts and networking. Regular meetings with stakeholders aroused interest and created support for the progress of the project. As a consequence, the roadmap process had to be scheduled in a shorter time period, not longer than 6 months for all three (or more) workshops. A compact process for all the steps kept the stakeholders more closely connected to the process and supported a more intensive exchange of knowledge or even co-creation process.

The stakeholders needed to see a clear benefit when participating in such a project and its workshops, so, the purpose of the roadmap had to be clearly formulated. The stakeholders contributed because they got to know that the co-creation process supported their mission. This had to be considered when inviting stakeholders to cooperation. The stakeholder groups in the DigiTeRRI project were very diverse, participants coming from university think and act different than people from SMEs, or public administration. Therefore, working out a concept for making clear the benefit for each specific stakeholder group would ensure a more reliable engagement of stakeholder in the various workshops. The stakeholder process had always been considered as a large think tank offering as many ideas and opinions as possible.

The evaluation of ideas, the interpretation and the analysis of the workshops, and deriving conclusions was the second step. For this work, either a core group of stakeholders reflected and summarized the workshop output, or the DigiTeRRI project team fulfilled this work according to the requirements of the stakeholder types.

In general, establishing a core group of stakeholders with representatives of the five stakeholder groups (science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public administration & policy makers, and civil society organisations) was crucial for getting high impact, acceptance, and approval for the work, in the case of DigiTeRRI the roadmapping results. So-called change agents or strong opinion leaders in the region should be attracted to the project work. They were drivers and they increased the impact, especially if they got an important role. Already existing collaboration network and clusters offered the first contacts for attracting stakeholders from e.g., the business sector.

All five stakeholder groups like to get a stage in each of the workshops and events so that they have the possibility to communicate their mission and to highlight their importance in the process and communicate their concerns.

The workshops for developing the vision statement and the roadmap goals and objectives had a different character than the implementation of the actions, so they attracted different actors of the regions. The workshops for developing the vision statement and the goals are characterised by creativity and strategic thinking. However,

creating an implementation plan required people willing to realise the actions actively for initiating the transition process.

The integrated RRI approach of DigiTeRRI claims to have all people affected involved into the process, but it was experienced that the different process steps attracted different actors. It is important to note that the stakeholder list is not a static one but can be seen as a dynamic instrument for attracting stakeholders depending on the process step. Managing these challenges, namely organising the different characters or personalities for the process steps (visioning is a different task than implementing a technology platform), needed a well-organized flow of information among the stakeholders also in one and the same organisation. Another important influence on the outcome was the background and knowledge of the representative of a stakeholder organisation. The composition of the stakeholders' group, their background and knowledge, their own mission and their individual strategies shaped the outputs and had impact on the transition path of territories. Furthermore, it is suggested to assume that not all stakeholders can take part in the roadmap process voluntary. Remuneration e.g., for travel might reduce the barrier for attending physical meetings in some groups and offer the equal framework for participation. Virtual meetings offered a form for low barrier participation in the workshops.

2.4 The RRI approach in DigiTeRRI

2.4.1 *Project work on integrated RRI approach*

It is hardly possible to introduce the RRI background in a short time in stakeholder workshops. The experiences made in the IAMRRI and SeeRRI projects³ led us to develop an integrated RRI approach in the DigiTeRRI project. Thus, the DigiTeRRI roadmapping process built on the concept of an integrated RRI process (Figure 2). The RRI process dimensions were covered by engaging the various stakeholders from the innovation ecosystem interlinked with the forward-looking methodology of roadmapping. The RRI key oriented questions were addressed to the stakeholders in the various workshops. In the analysis and interpretation of the workshop outputs RRI trained co-

³ The project partners MUL, MAT, NRI, WeDo and AIT have gained experience in at least one of these projects.

workers were engaged. They checked if the statements had a relation to RRI and in what way.

RRI integrated roadmapping covers the RRI dimensions.

This process is diverse & inclusive, anticipative & reflective, open & transparent, responsive & adaptive.

(Source Nguyen et al. 2021, D3.2)

Figure 2: DigiTeRRI common framework.

2.4.2 Lessons learnt from the DigiTeRRI RRI approach

RRI was integrated into the DigiTeRRI roadmapping and stakeholder process. This DigiTeRRI RRI approach interlinks the RRI process dimensions as presented in **Figure 2** with a co-creation process with the stakeholders from the innovation ecosystem (science & research, education, industry & business incl. SMEs, public administration, and civil society organisations). In addition, the strategic work in the stakeholder workshops covered goals and actions also addressing the RRI keys⁴ (ethics, science education, open access, gender equality, and public engagement). In this way, the DigiTeRRI RRI approach was clearly understandable for all stakeholders

It turned out that the developed goals and actions were oriented towards RRI key topics and showed the need for actions in gender equality, science education, ethics, and open access to succeed in the digital transition. Digital

⁴ Besides the goals and actions for the digital transformation.

innovation as core topic was addressed in many actions such as establishing digital platforms, enhancing entrepreneurship, or building knowledge in digitalisation.

It was shown that RRI could be a practical concept to control digitization at different levels: 1) at a political-strategic level with territorially elected people; 2) at executive level in companies, mostly when designing new digital products/services; 3) at the citizen level to attract people to science.

And even the COVID-19 pandemic has contributed to more concern for RRI.

Table 8. Strength and Weaknesses of the DigiTeRRI RRI approach.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder groups were engaged in the project initiatives such as scientists, students, engineers, entrepreneurs, cities or the public. Balanced gender representation in the stakeholder groups was considered. The RRI concept was generally highly stimulating for people discovering them. The RRI approach was a multilevel concept and relevant for the main societal challenges. The DigiTeRRI RRI approach was a pathfinder for pointing out the way and what to focus on in the digital transformation of the regions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The RRI approach could not address all challenges in the digital transformation in the territories. The RRI concept in its core is still difficult to communicate to the stakeholders. An explicit approach would have been too overburdened for the overall project idea and the challenge of digitalisation. The RRI terms were not easy to communicate to all at local level. Confronting the stakeholders directly with the RRI terminology would overburden them. There was a lack of link between RRI and ecology.

Table 9. Opportunities and Weaknesses of DigiTeRRI RRI approach.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RRI approach offers a guide to address the societal needs in roadmap design and actions. Stakeholder groups were engaged in the project initiatives such as scientists, students, females, engineers, entrepreneurs, cities or the general public. • The RRI work is an opportunity to discover and settle RRI approach not known at local level for all kind of structures. • The applied DigiTeRRI RRI approach works with inclusiveness, making people affected of a change involved in the transformation process. This can be applicable in other areas on change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confronting the stakeholders / the actors of the innovation ecosystem in the regions directly with RRI confuses them (these stakeholders), because of the quite complex approach. • The concept of RRI is not sufficiently taken up and understood on a territorial scale. • Never being able to close the gap to the stakeholders and making them understand how to interpret RRI and how to use the concept.

2.4.3 Recommendations regarding the DigiTeRRI RRI approach

From a communications perspective, we have used images, graphics and text that reinforce the RRI dimensions of inclusivity, anticipation, responsiveness and reflexivity, along with the principles of gender equality, science literacy, ethics, open access and public engagement and community Participation. The development of RRI-focused visuals implemented at territorial level had led to various internal discussions of the project team to find appropriate visual concepts. This process resulted in a better understanding of RRI within the project team and appropriate visualizations for the area under consideration. It turned out that the understanding of the RRI concepts in the implementation of actual actions at local level had led to different approaches that were deeply rooted in sociocultural aspects. That became obvious in the discussions around how people or situations should be represented graphically. The use of visual / graphical presentation had unblocked deeper debates on how equality, participation or inclusiveness had to be represented so the message was clear. That meant going beyond the inherent bias of words and understanding the great potential of images to convey complex concepts so they could be understood by a broader audience.

The RRI concept obviously could be easily adapted for people that neither do research nor technology development. Stakeholders tried to use digital technologies within their structure (company, association, public body) or in other entities (clusters, academic...). They found it educational and motivating to use the RRI concept to give responsible meaning to their initiatives. So, there was a paradox: RRI wasn't easy to understand, but it was powerful when it was adopted. It is recommended to focus on the message of RRI in context of digitalisation, and not so strongly on the approach itself (implicit/integrated solution). Communicating the RRI aspects implicitly with more real life-oriented keywords would be better accepted at local level.

2.5 Intra-territorial collaboration among the regional project teams

2.5.1 *Intra-territorial collaboration in project work*

The project team in each territory consisted of representatives of science & research, from public authorities, and of an organisation close to industry (business cluster or network and start up service), the so-called Triple Helix representatives. In Sweden, Värmlands läns landsting (Värmland) represented the public authority having the responsibility of regional development, The Paper Province ekonomisk förening (PP) was the link to industry and business, and Karlstads Universitet (KAU) came from science & research. In France, Grand E-nov (GEN) is the regional innovation and foreign investments attractivity mainly funded by Region Grand-Est (Public authority) and Chamber of commerce of Grand-Est, MATERIALIA (MAT) a competitiveness cluster (business, innovation, training), and Université de Lorraine (UL). In Styria, Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur (Bruck) represented the city of Bruck an der Mur, Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben (ZAT) which is a Start-up centre in Leoben in Austria, and Montanuniversitaet Leoben (MUL) brought the expertise in science & research, knowledge and technology management and RRI. **Figure 3** shows the partner structure in the pilot territories and the DigiTeRRI project consortium.

Figure 3: Triple Helix Partner structure in each DigiTeRRI Territory.

Three further partners were from outside these three territories, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) Austria, Nordland Research Institute (NRI) Norway, both are research organisation and responsible for coordination and framework, and WeDo Project intelligence made easy S.L. (WeDo) Spain, for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation work.

The constellation of the Triple Helix project partners supported the collaboration between the project partners inside the territory enormously, because (a) the different perspectives and knowledgebase of the actors of an innovation ecosystem could be discussed and brought into the stakeholder engagement work, (b) the knowledge and expertise brought in by the stakeholders have been better understood and thus better further processed, (c) this project team structure enhanced the access to various stakeholders. Complementary skills, use of collaborative tools in parallel with direct contacts are part of the reasons of this high level of collaboration. The share of the different challenges between all members was important.

2.5.2 Lessons learnt from intra-territorial collaboration

Table 10. Strength and Weaknesses in the intra-territorial collaboration inside the project team.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different competence and access to all defined stakeholder groups, good interaction and high flexibility in COVID-19 circumstances, strong interaction of project team, sharing of workload, balanced gender distribution in the project team. • Experts about the different domains of digitalisation within the project team members provided a systemic view of the problems, e.g., the small and tight group of people was the backbone of the Värmland team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The different culture of the project organisation (research – public authority – industry & business) was a challenge, needed a good communication, and each of them had different expectations. Differing views on the time needed to complete tasks within the team require strict project management. • Geographical distance between actors in Grand-Est region – not so many face-to-face meetings are possible. • One DigiTeRRI territorial project team had no representative from the regional government, but from a municipality. This gave different levels for acting. A governmental partner had more power to influence the strategy of the territory, whereas partners such as municipalities have more power to implement concrete actions for business and citizens in their area.

Table 11. Opportunities and Threats in intra-territorial collaboration inside the project team.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DigiTeRRI considered the whole innovation ecosystem. Therefore, a wider view to regional necessities is needed. This can be provided by multiorganizational and interdisciplinary teams. • In addition, other collaboration fields (outside the DigiTeRRI tasks) were developed, and collaboration have started. • The territorial project team increased the understanding of each other's organization and built-up knowledge for future project collaboration. • To share experience in managing groups of stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DigiTeRRI initiatives compete with already existing territorial initiatives or organizations which might see this as a competitor and interference in their own affairs. • If only one person is representing a project partner makes the team vulnerable, when it comes to illness and diseases such as COVID-19, etc. So, sharing the competence might be more helpful for the progress of a roadmapping when time span should be shortened. However, this depends on the available resources.

2.5.3 Recommendations for intra-territorial collaboration

The Triple Helix structure in the project team (each territorial team has a representative from university, from public authority, and industry / business cluster) was powerful. The constellation of the Triple Helix project partners supported the collaboration between the project partners inside the territory enormously, because (a) the different perspective of the actors of an innovation ecosystem could be discussed and brought into the stakeholder engagement work, (b) the knowledge and expertise brought in by the stakeholders had been better understood and thus better further processed, (c) these project team structure enhanced the access to various stakeholders and resources. It is therefore recommended to have a similar composition in the project team as the triple helix structure of the stakeholders. A balanced composition of genders is also important.

Furthermore, like any transition (climate, energy, etc.), digitization required a systemic approach. In fact, action variables and decisions were linked. The DigiTeRRI roadmapping process stimulated this systemic approach among the group of roadmap designers as it involved contributors in a collective and consistency vision, goals and objectives definition and action plan elaboration. This transition required digital competencies in the regional teams and access to experts in the field of roadmapping.

A critical point was the connection between area representatives working in the field of digitization and the DigiTeRRI team. There are still close ties between the companies in Styria and Värmland due to the smaller size of the territory. In Grand-Est, a huge region, particular attention was paid to informing the area leaders. Some DigiTeRRI actions of Grand-Est were dedicated to the integration of RRI into the current regional strategy on digitisation. The establishment of an advisory board made it possible to broaden the representativeness of regional partnerships (e.g., Region Grand-Est in Grand-Est) or to add academic partners to provide feedback.

2.6 Cross-territorial collaboration in DigiTeRRI

2.6.1 *Project work on cross-territorial collaboration*

The cross territorial exchange was promoted especially during the implementation phase, in the last year of the project. Cross-territorial actions were performed, e.g., the student union exchange, the cross regional cooperation event, the training for digital fairs or in the incubator exchange.

The workshop of DAMI4.0⁵ at Karlstad University on 13th September 2022 afternoon, brought experts from universities, industry, and SMEs from Värmland and the DigiTeRRI consortium partners together, where experts from France and Austria discussed on the stage with experts from Värmland.

The final DigiTeRRI conference on 20th and 21st October 2022 underlined the importance of exchanging results, knowledge, approaches across disciplines and territories and opened up to speakers and cases from other segments and regions (<https://conference.digiterri.eu/>). DigiTeRRI integrated RRI approach was a powerful instrument to learn about other territories and cultures. The entire DigiTeRRI team worked very constructively and closely together.

⁵ (www.kau.se/dami40/om-dami40/dami-workshop).

2.6.2 *Lessons learnt from cross-territorial collaboration*

The DigiTeRRI roadmaps were developed for each of the three territories, for Styria, for Grand-Est, and for Värmland. The goal of territorial roadmaps was to focus on project work in the territories and consequently on local needs. The cross-territorial development was not pronounced or favoured and thus there was not so much commitment and resources for cross regional collaboration of stakeholders. Overall, the three territories were quite autonomous, focusing mostly on the activities within each territory.

At the roadmap definition stage, joint actions, knowledge sharing, and joint analysis only concern DigiTeRRI project members. This internal mutual learning was very important to share experience and helped to build a common knowhow about the methodology to be applied. There were opportunities to get to know the partners and the strengths of the partners from the other territories. Opportunities for cross-regional cooperation were identified later in the project after territorial actions had been prioritised. This was obviously a strong limitation on cross-territorial collaboration opportunities. However, some collaborations were put in place:

- The participation of DigiTeRRI members from other territories to actions performed in Styria (start-up meeting, digital exhibition for SMEs) or in Värmland (industry 4.0 seminar) among others.
- The common participation to two workshops held in Grand-Est (ICE-IAMOT Congress) aiming at the dissemination of DigiTeRRI methodology and outcomes;
- The elaboration of an app with a quiz about professional opportunities in the digital world associating WeDo and other territories;
- The elaboration of a training kit helping the transfer of one module developed in Grand-Est to Värmland in the domain of responsible digital project management.

Table 12. Strength and Weaknesses of cross-territorial collaboration.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cross-territorial collaboration provided a wider view and different ideas. It gave access to other experts, interesting contacts, option of co-creation and co-learning, power of graphical element could be demonstrated. • Cross-territorial collaboration had motivated the improvement of territorial awareness about RRI. • The communication process and the great competences of WeDo for communicating the project results with visual / graphical presentation strengthened the collaboration between all partners. • The cross-territorial collaboration during the implementation phase was supported by the Smart Sheet tool, which gave access to knowledge from the other territories for all partners, also the partners outside the territories, namely NRI, WeDo, AIT. • The cross-territorial discussion helped to understand the situation of different territories and also how different actions can look. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was not always easy to understand the partners from the other territories and their missions, especially in the beginning of the project. • Fewer physical meetings due to COVID-19 pandemic than planned.

Table 13. Opportunities and Threats of cross-territorial collaboration.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-territorial collaboration provides learning, knowledge exchange, networking, identification of common interest, and generation of cross regional initiatives. • Cross-territorial collaboration improves the preparation of the actions because additional points of view are brought in. • The poster session at the DigiTeRRI conference supported the communication of implemented actions to other regions even after the conference, because the posters are also available online. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not enough resources for cross-territorial collaboration between stakeholders from outside the project team is a risk. • Cross regional collaboration within DigiTeRRI is in competition with the external partnership that the stakeholders already have. In a period of low resources and COVID-19, new long-distance collaboration is difficult to promote especially to small structures (SMEs, Retailers, Associations).

2.6.3 Recommendations for cross-territorial collaboration

Well and clearly defined cross-territorial goals and cross-regional collaboration already in the proposal would easier lead to implement this collaboration, especially when stakeholders outside the project team are engaged. Also, if some cross-territorial initiatives would be already created at the beginning of the project, it would made it easier to implement them. However, at the beginning of such a project common understanding had to be developed first. The benefit and the added value of the cross-regional collaboration had to be worked out very clearly for the stakeholders from outside the project team.

Higher commitment for implementing the cross-territorial collaboration was needed, and earlier in the project. This should be brought up early enough by the facilitators in the roadmapping processes. Due to the fact that stakeholders' participation in the vision statement and goals development were often not the same for implementing the actions is a challenge. Involving the stakeholders who implement these cross-territorial actions supported the success of the work. In addition, specific facilitation for trans-territorial actions was necessary, also with communication and marketing activities. Carefully involvement of organisations at same/similar institutional level avoided the mismatch of interests.

Finding commonalities in each territory that could be explored in joint tasks or meetings could help building cross-territorial collaboration. This should be included in the design of the work plan and agreed early of the project. Stakeholders from the various regions and with actors from industry, education, policymaking were identified for becoming part of a territorial working group, defining common interests, and participated in discussions and reflection. In addition, financial resources were needed to help stakeholders invest together in new partnerships in another area. However, the participation of other territories was highly appreciated by the participants both during the seminar with professionals and during the ICE/IAMOT Congress. This cross-regional cooperation strengthened the image of the local organizers.

2.7 Implementation of actions

2.7.1 *Project work on implementation of actions*

In order to verify the effectiveness of the project work and start the change process, 12 actions per region were implemented during the project period. To support the implementation a monitoring tool was developed and used. The implementation team had monthly update meetings to track the development in the implementation process (see Myhrén, 2022, D5.1). The implementation of the actions could be controlled for instance with a Smart Sheet system, or Excel, or similar tools, to make this work transparent for all persons in charge. The Smart Sheet Dashboard made visible the implementation progress, as [Figure 4](#) shows (the left part in orange indicates Grand-Est region, the part in the middle in green Styria, and the right part in blue shows Värmland). This implementation work had encouraged the success of the project very much.

(Source: This screen shot was taken in end of May 2022.)

Figure 4: Smart Sheet Dashboard.

During DigiTeRRI online meetings, reports of the on-going actions were given to other territories. A common understanding was then possible about the specificities of each territory about “the way of doing things”. The meetings on implementation promoted to have more cross-territorial exchange and activities.

In addition, the perceived immediate impact of the project was evaluated. This is to identify the changes in the target population with respect to responsible digitalisation in the participating territories. As a small-scale post-project impact evaluation based on an online survey, quantitative evaluation, covered all implemented actions and other activities in DigiTeRRI. Target groups of the survey were the actions’ participants, the regional stakeholders and the actions’ managers in all three regions, Grand-Est, Styria, and Värmland. It collected and analysed the perceived changes during their DigiTeRRI involvement. A core message of this monitoring is summarized in the following paragraph.

Participation in DigiTeRRI was highly valued by the regional stakeholders and actions' participants. Most respondents rated the DigiTeRRI support for responsible digitalisation very positively in general. It helped mainly with respect to increasing awareness for open access, digitalisation in education and life-long learning, but also inclusiveness and gender balance. Less impact was seen in the more technical areas like data security and privacy issues, especially from industry representatives (see Paier et al., 2022, D5.2).

The three main aspects from the monitoring are (i) digitalisation strategies and practices, (ii) changes in digitalisation maturity, and (iii) changes in networks are also highlighted an “evaluated framework and measures” work (Stegmann McCallion et al., 2022, D5.3) have to be understood together. Changes in digitalisation strategies and practices were explored as awareness building, capacity building, and impact innovation among the actors. The changes in digitalisation strategies and practices were connected with the changes in digitalisation maturity, earlier focus was on technical digitalisation aspects such as the technical hardware and infrastructure.

2.7.2 Lessons learnt from implementation work

Implementing actions and measures required the involvement of the stakeholders and people affected by these actions. However, the stakeholders who had developed the goals and objectives, even they had defined the specific necessary actions for closing the gaps were not the same people, who implemented them. As already mentioned under “stakeholder engagement”, the strategically thinking and working people in an organization were often not the same people who then implemented the defined measures. This implies (i) resources for the people implementing the actions and measures, (ii) a knowledge transfer inside the organisation, (iii) a change in the organisation which means also involving the people who take part in the implementation of the actions in an earlier stage. However, by implementing actions and measures other persons were attracted and thus the work received more awareness and impact.

Actions implementation was highly depending on the objectives. Political actions aiming the integration of RRI in the digitalisation strategy of the territory required numerous meetings and a lot of time. Actions aiming at an increased awareness of some targeted beneficiaries required more methodological preparation to integrate digital and responsiveness aspects.

Table 14. Strength and Weaknesses of the implementation of action process.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of actions made visible the impact of the roadmap work and thus supports the transition into a digitalised region. • Concrete defined and implemented actions brought sustainable impact e.g., scan and shop (Styria), Digi-lab, knowledge building, and collaboration opportunities. • The implementation of actions brought digitalisation to a larger number of stakeholders because the implementation needs the collaboration of various stakeholders. • The implementation of actions raised the awareness about RRI and digitalisation in the stakeholder group and in the region. • The implementation of actions inspired the active partners and thus succeeds by direct contacts with beneficiaries. • The implementation of actions supported better understanding of the wide range of opinions about RRI and simultaneously develops new knowledge about digitalisation and train people regarding RRI. • The alignment of vision statement with the roadmap goals, objectives, and actions especially the co-creation within the stakeholder groups made the implementation of actions relevant for the stakeholders from the industrial sector. • The implementation promoted the transition to the need of stakeholders, brings new ideas, and have a various type of actions and different goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders are needed for the implementation, which was a challenge (a) during COVID-19, (b) too many events after COVID-19, (c) short time (during the project duration). • DigiTeRRI partners and stakeholders from other DigiTeRRI territories had not enough resources and time to participate in actions of a specific DigiTeRRI territory. Transnational activities were planned, however would need more resources. • There were limitations regarding financial resources. • Each action needed a person in charge of (time, costs, etc.).

Table 15. Opportunities and Threats of the implementation of action process.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The implementation promotes the transition in accordance with the need of stakeholders, brought new ideas, actions and different goals. • Implementation of actions was further a possibility to validate the roadmap through pragmatic activities. • The implementation created new contacts and collaborations between some actors (e.g., “Communicasciences”, CCI Alsace Eurométropole...). It strengthened collaboration between stakeholders and created new networks inside the territories. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the frame of DigiTeRRI project there were not enough time and budget. With more resources far reaching actions for pushing the transition into digitalisation would be possible. • There could be a lack of relevance to some stakeholders due to the failure to engage them earlier in the process.

2.7.3 Recommendations regarding the implementation of actions

The implementation of actions and the monitoring to create impact need a good management and appropriate tools. Smart Sheet tool facilitated the monitoring of implementation. It was used by all partners. Regularly exchange meetings helped to promote cross territorial interaction and learning with in DigiTeRRI project team.

The implementation of actions and measures depended essentially on stakeholders. Some stakeholders were perfect for idea generation and new impulses in a roadmapping process. For implementation, more powerful stakeholders were needed in most cases. This referred to power, legitimacy, ability to implement, and financial - and human resources. The implementation of actions worked well in case people or organisations responsible for the implementation were equipped with enough resources.

2.8 Digital transition achieved in DigiTeRRI

2.8.1 Output on digital transition

The process of transitioning one traditional territory to become a digitalised territory was called digital transformation. The monitoring of the implemented actions unveiled that despite the short time span of 2 ½ years, significant changes in digitalisation strategies and practices were observed (Paier et al., 2022, D5.2). The most radical change was reported in strategy changes in digital communication, digital teaching and training, and although the COVID-19 pandemic was seen as the main driver, this strategy shift was also attributed to some extent to the participation in DigiTeRRI. On the other hand, surprisingly, a considerable number of organisations across all institutional sectors still lacked an explicit digitalisation strategy. DigiTeRRI was acknowledged a significant contribution to actual change in digital practices within the last two years, albeit it was conceded that communicating RRI to the public in connection to digitalisation remained a challenge. Improvements in digitalisation maturity were measurable and were partly attributed to DigiTeRRI participation. On a wide range of management dimensions (strategy, leadership, products, operations etc.) the digital maturity of organisations had been rated. The respondents clearly reported an increase on a well-known digital maturity scale. It was possible to significantly reduce the share of digital unawareness in organisations and to step up the digitalisation ladder. Only the highest level of digitalisation, “transformed” seemed to be out of reach within a short period like the DigiTeRRI participation provided.

2.8.2 Lessons learnt from digital transition

DigiTeRRI contributed fully to the digital transition by a responsible approach. It created general awareness in the territories and highlighted the main goals and needs. It worked out a strategic instrument and a path for further development to digitalisation of the society and economy. It demonstrated in various actions how the digitalisation will change or life and show needed improvements.

The DigiTeRRI roadmap defined by territorial stakeholders includes a wide range of objectives and targeted changes such as public awareness, RRI integration in territorial strategies, education and trainings, etc. The three DigiTeRRI territories developed the goals, objectives, and actions in the different DigiTeRRI roadmap domains (Knowledge & skills, Technology, Networks & collaboration, Infrastructure, Culture & values, Leadership, business & market, Communication). The COVID-19 pandemic forced to digitalise processes.

Note a particular aspect: There was impact of DigiTeRRI on territorial policy. In each territory, thanks to interrelation between local representatives and DigiTeRRI members RRI was taken in account in the current digital political strategy. It was an impact closer to an “influence” than a “change”.

Table 16. Strength and Weaknesses of the digital transition in DigiTeRRI.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The stocktaking and mapping gave a good starting point and provided the basis for a common understanding. • A questionnaire helped to bring a clear view on the current situation of the roadmap implementation. • A wide and stakeholder-based analysis helped to understand the needs. • Stakeholders had a diverse level of implementation in digitalisation. • A digital transition was achieved by a RRI responsible approach from different actions. • The formation of a digitalisation network is a very important initiative to commonly develop knowledge and skills within digitalisation/industrial automation. • But they also took on the challenging work to increase the attractiveness of work in companies in the industry in Värmland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was not enough knowledge about digital transformation inside the stakeholder groups. Especially stakeholders from society lack the knowledge to follow the digital transition. • Tailored actions are needed to make the society digitally fit. Society seems to need a more basic knowledge and capacities to turn in a digital world. • Inclusion of various stakeholder groups was not realized yet, e.g., females need other support for joining the digital transition (one example here could be family management). • Some priorities were defined by the stakeholders, then some domains were not impacted, this includes hard product production (sensors for example), automation of manufacturing production lines. • The applied DigiTeRRI approach was complex and would require long-term financing, much longer than 3 years, for a comprehensive transition.

Table 17. Opportunities and Threats of the digital transition in DigiTeRRI.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS (RISKS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a high potential for reaching out to other global territories, new innovation and development, compensating loss of human resources with digital solution, attracting employees globally, digital offers of public administration can make procedure simpler and less time consuming. • Digital jobs and home office give more flexibility and reduction of travel times and resource for mobility. • Continued collaboration between different stakeholders as a result of DigiTeRRI to enhance the digital transformation in the region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People who are not digitally fit do not have access to public online administration and hence are discriminated against. • Low educated or low qualified people will lose their jobs and incomes. • Digital jobs and home office might lead to risk of social isolation.

2.8.3 Recommendations regarding the digital transformation

The DigiTeRRI project revealed that a clear starting point helps to create a common understanding of all stakeholders, about the challenge of the roadmapping and the change process itself. It helped to make the process visible to all stakeholders and created a positive attitude of all stakeholders to the transition. The different points of view, experiences from different sectoral structures (e.g., research, education, clusters, associations, innovation and economic actors) needed a thorough analysis and management of derived support actions.

Some aspects about digital transformation were rather technical, such as infrastructures and hardware (ITOT, sensors, interoperability among other). But even experts in these domains totally admitted the importance of a territorial dynamic that could improve individual initiatives. Hence, companies totally agreed about educational priorities. Moreover, companies considered that their own success in digitalisation required a change in their relations with their environment (academia, public institutions and also citizens). Thus, the systemic approach of DigiTeRRI seemed efficient when considering digital challenges.

DigiTeRRI focused deliberately on some actions about awareness and knowledge creation which were the basic variables to stimulate the use of digital technology and to avoid digital divide. This was one main asset of the DigiTeRRI project.

The results of the DigiTeRRI integrated RRI approach gave more smooth measures for transition so that all the societal actors can join the change process. So, it is concluded that a stakeholder process should be applied if the society is asked to undergo changes especially caused by technologies. The DigiTeRRI RRI approach and the roadmapping process included the needs and challenges of all societal groups, in our case e.g., it highlighted the gender equality topic. Roadmapping becomes more powerful when coupled with other territorial strategies such as the S3 strategy.

3 CONCLUSION

The three DigiTeRRI regional territories, Grand-Est, Styria, and Värmland, currently undergo the change from the traditional industrial production e.g., materials such as steel, paper and pulp production, automotive, aerospace industry, or production industry in general to a digitalised industry. Each of this territory is an innovation ecosystem, which consists of actors who are doing innovation activities and the interaction of these actors. The entirety of private and public organizations and individuals, which contribute by their activities and interactions to the creation and diffusion of new technologies, new products, or new knowledge, build an innovation system. A smooth interplay between the actors is fundamental for a successful industry and business in a region. The composition of the following aspects and forces are the basis for flourishing innovation ecosystems, the conditions from policy makers, the knowledge and technology creation in a region on universities or research organizations, the collaboration between research and industry, the highly educated employees, either from the region or also attracted from the best education places in the world, the infrastructure in the region. The success of a region (which is the summary of the economy and the wellbeing of the people there) depends on the constructive interplay and collaboration between these elements. Therefore, industry & business have a big interest to co-create the future together with all other actors in a region.

The DigiTeRRI approach helped to include all relevant actors into the transition process. It considered the forces for a flourishing innovation ecosystem, namely the conditions from policy makers, the knowledge and technology creation in a region on universities or research organizations, the collaboration between research and industry, the employees, either from the region or also attracted from the best education places in the world, and the infrastructure in the region. The success of a region, which is the summary of the economy and the wellbeing of the people there, depends on the constructive interplay and collaboration between these elements. Therefore, industry & business have a big interest to co-create the future together with all other actors in a region. To have a smooth and well considered transition to digital industry areas the DigiTeRRI project did a strategic future planning for all the three territories using the roadmapping methodology. Starting from a classical roadmap this methodology was developed for the multi organisational and stakeholder engaged process. Since the “Responsible Research Innovation” approach intends to include the society in decision making processes for such an important change, the developed integrated RRI approach was a central point for the establishment of the roadmap plan of the three territories.

The RRI approach applied in DigiTeRRI combined the strategic forward-looking methodologies roadmapping with stakeholder engagement to develop possible futures for the transition into digitalisation. This approach should strengthen the innovation ecosystem in the territory including all stakeholders and generates added value. RRI

was operationalised by combining a roadmapping process with stakeholder engagement, and explicitly by addressing the RRI keys (ethics, science education, open access, gender equality, public engagement) in the development of the roadmaps' goals and objectives. The DigiTeRRI process (i) mapped the current situation of the innovation ecosystem with data from science publications, EU projects, and patents, and collected best practices on digitalisation and RRI at the beginning of the project; (ii) generated a vision statement as a guide for the roadmap; (iii) developed goals, objectives, and actions necessary to reach these objectives; (iv) and implemented first actions already in each of the three territories.

The integrated DigiTeRRI RRI and roadmapping approach was applied very successfully and with great impact in each of the three territories. The interlink between co-creating a roadmap with stakeholders, which implicit brought the RRI process dimension, and with addressing the RRI keys achieved (a) learnings for the engaged stakeholders regarding RRI and regarding transformation into a digitalised territory, (b) pathways and concrete actions regarding the importance of promoting digital skills in schools and especially for girls, (c) stronger collaboration between the stakeholders inside the territories, e.g., collaboration between universities and industry and SMEs, (d) knowledge creation and dissemination of the importance of RRI with regard to the implication of technology and innovation on society and environment.

DigiTeRRI project supported awareness and capacity building and impacted innovation. It created a regional digitalisation network in all territories and initiated new networks of stakeholders acting on the global market. In Region Värmland and Grand-Est, the DigiTeRRI work was used also for formulating the Regional Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategy. It was envisaged that these roadmapping processes, which was co-created with actors from the territories. This DigiTeRRI methodology influenced the S3 strategy development process; learnings from DigiTeRRI were applied in the S3 development. The DigiTeRRI learning was described as being a solution provider to interested SMEs, the regional authority took on a facilitating role and provided expertise on how the SMEs can further develop. Furthermore, Grand-Est developed together with stakeholders in DigiTeRRI the integration of KPIs issued from RRI in the S3 for the period 2020-2027. Styria had a strong focus on the engagement of civil society. Styria had a balanced mixture of the conducted goals and implemented actions for policy, for knowledge generating and networking actions. Styria also established a platform, organised events for networking and exchange of different stakeholder groups. The intention was to build up knowledge, get opened up for other European regions and new cooperation to manage the transition. This more bottom-up approach can be interpreted as typical result for civil society stakeholder engagement.

Gender equality and female empowerment turned out to be a key issue in the change process. Strengthening of science education of young students and pupils played an important role in many implemented actions. Co-creation, co-learning and knowledge building or taking new opportunities of platforms were the key element which will help to manage the transition to digital territory.

The integrated RRI approach effected the values in companies, or cultural values of the overall society and initiates discussion on responsible innovation. Working with the stakeholders in the territories in this RRI integrated way created new perspectives for the everyday life in the stakeholders' organisations. The DigiTeRRI final conference “Best Practices for Digitalisation Strategies in Regions” (<https://conference.digiterri.eu/>) was an excellent platform for exchanging experiences on the integration of RRI and this value change. All three territories presented finally how this DigiTeRRI approach brought RRI to their territory. During the final conference some success examples from companies and other territories were presented who successfully applied the DigiTeRRI integrated RRI roadmap process and benefit from the lessons learnt of the project. The DigiTeRRI integrated RRI approach initiated a change on the way to digital transition in the project team members and their territories. First analysis revealed the positive impact of the project.

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